

LIBRARY THEORY AND RESEARCH PROJECT DATA CURATOR

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Data curator: who is s/he? a survey of international and interdisciplinary perspectives

Project Team

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Members of LTR Section involved in the Project are supported by external collaborators:

- Lars Svensson (l.svensson@dnb.de) from the Information Technology Section collaborating with the Project Team.
- Two students are collaborating with the Project Team: Frank Sposito (ontology) and Ana Pervan (Literature review)
- Two external collaborators have been added to the Project Team: Andrew Cox (Univ. Sheffield) and Vittore Casarosa (ISTI CNR - ontology).

Aims and objectives

The project aims to clarify the role of Data Curator collecting perceptions and definitions about the role and competencies of the data curator at an international and interdisciplinary level.

The objectives are

- to prepare a taxonomy (a list of terms in hierarchical structure)
- and an ontology, using a formal representation of a set of concepts.

The research questions addressed in this study are:

- How is data curation currently defined by its practitioners working in the field?
- What specific professional vocabularies are used to describe the data curator's core competencies?
- What are the data curator's primary roles and responsibilities?
- What are key the educational qualifications and areas of expertise required of successful data curators?

- How do these vocabularies, roles, skills, and responsibilities vary by country and region around the world?

Methodology and tools to collect data

First, the Team has conducted a broad, comprehensive, and systematic survey of the literature related to the area of digital curation. Next, a subgroup conducted content analysis of job descriptions. In the second phase the Team disseminated a questionnaire, and conducted interviews with data curators working in the field.

No Professional Association until now has been involved in developing the competencies of data curator and so the Team started from labour market, with a bottom up approach focusing on perceptions of competencies of data curator and employers of data curators. In the first phase of the project, we concentrated on analyzing job announcements for data curators in libraries, archives, university departments, and research centers.

First Phase

In the first phase of the project, data were collected through literature review and analysis of job description. Both the literature review and the analysis of the job description has been focused on the United States, where the research and practice on data curator are more advanced.

The goal of analyzing job postings was to examine the titles used for data curation positions and to understand what are the roles and qualifications of data curators. This approach is, of course, from the perspective of employers, but it allows us to see what terminology is being used and what are the expectations of people hired for these positions. For the purpose of this project, we searched selected online sources to identify position announcements with data curation responsibilities. Data collection was conducted in the fall 2015. The following sites were searched to locate job announcements for data curators and positions with data curation responsibilities.

- American Library Association (ALA) Job list: <http://joblist.ala.org/>
- Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR): <http://www.clir.org/fellowships/postdoc/info/dc-science>
- Code4lib: <http://jobs.code4lib.org/jobs/data-curation/>
- Indeed: one search .all jobs: <http://www.indeed.com/>
- Selected data curation centers

A first Glossary and the Job description terminology has been produced in this first phase. From the literature and documentary review first analysis, AP e KM have noted a variety of terminology used, with different terms used for the same concept.

In the job descriptions KM has evidenced different requirements, including LIS degree, subject specialization, fellowship and corresponding different qualifications.

The initial coverage of the survey to EU and USA has been extended to Asia, LA and Africa after the decisions taken at the October meeting of the Team. For extending the research to not English speaking countries, other members of LTR SC have been contacted:

Korea Taekyung Kim <taekyung.ktk@gmail.com>

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Russia lisa@spsl.nsc.ru" <lisa@spsl.nsc.ru>

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Second Phase

In the second phase of the project, from November to now, we have planned to interview information professionals who work as data curators. A questionnaire has also prepared, to satisfy the requirement of multilingualism together with that of enlarging the sample.

Interview Guide and questionnaire

For the survey of Data Curator we have decided to consider focusing on interviewing employees and employers in **non-English** speaking countries because of the limited resources we have available to conduct the interviews and the already existing information available on data curation in English speaking countries in the literature and in the job descriptions.

IFLA LTR can contribute to new knowledge to the topic of Data Curation if we are investigating the extent to which libraries in countries where the other IFLA official languages other than English is spoken are employing individuals as data curators and what those employers and employees perceive as their needs for skills and training.

A draft questionnaire has been agreed and is accessible here:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HBXiuHodipapbzOXbtzTneFg9488s32msucr9EklhGY/edit?usp=sharing>

Interviews to key informants was using the Interview Guide:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1P-kgaJ26-Icw4WQWTm0pqVxZh4yIFeYHJfZxd7nYtgA/edit?usp=sharing>

Conferences participation

The Team decided to plan the participation to Workshops and Panels during Conferences to gain information and meeting key informants.

TW, AP, AMT and HKO have participated to the Bobcatss Conference in Lyon in January¹.

The Workshop has stimulated the discussion on a shared vocabulary, to understand the different aspects of the data curation in Europe, where most of participants came from. Countries of participants were: France, Finland, Germany, Italy, Netherland, Switzerland and U.S.

AMT, VC, AP, KM, FS have participated to a Panel during LIDA Conference in Zadar². One of the LIDA Conference topics was Data curation. A panel on Data curation in Asia was also organized inside LIDA to inform the evolution of research and practice in this area. The preliminary findings from the Panel discussion indicated that different terms are used to describe various roles for professionals working with organizing, managing, and preserving data. Preservation, digital curation and data curation are used with different interpretations in different countries. Data curation is an emergent field and precise vocabulary has yet to mature.

¹

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KGuN6r-D2aYweQpLm_EcUQNNGO9cI9qOM6LQuarEwJ0/edit?usp=sharing

² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BbAWW0aCL3-aHEaXdazarG0pg_6MClhdW2D2_jkPEOA/edit?usp=sharing

LIS education

For doing the research in LIS Schools, has been co-opted Andrew Cox Professor in Sheffield University. He will collaborate with the Project Team and will collaborate with Carolyn Rankin and Beth Sandore for LIS curriculum analysis and interviews to professors.

The activities done and ongoing are listed in the following Table:

Task	When	Who	Milestone
Literature and documentary review	September 30th Sharing Bibliography	AP KM	Glossary of terms Annotated Bibliography
Job description	Started in November 2015 and ongoing	KM, FS	Position Description Terminology
Skype Virtual meetings	October 15th October 30th November 17th December 21st February 16th	ALL	Decisions taken: 1. Extend to ASIA, LA, Africa 2. Multilingual Glossary 3. Focus on Data Librarian
Structured interview to data curators themselves and the people who hire data curators	October 15th <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draft interview structure November Interviews guide completed Ethics Statement Ongoing	USA: KM, TW, PO EU: HO, AMT, AP ASIA, AFRICA, LA: LTR members to be contacted	Interviews in Europe (European sub-Team) List of data curators and institutions in USA, EU, LA, Asia, Africa
Questionnaire to be sent to selected LIS institutions	October 15th <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draft questionnaire February Questionnaire agreed Ongoing	USA: KM, TW, PO EU: HO, AMT, AP ASIA, AFRICA, LA: LTR members to be contacted	Interviews to educators and professors (AC, CR and AMT) List of LIS Schools in USA, EU, LA, Asia, Africa
Workshop BOBCATSSS	January 2016 Focus group with participants	TW, AMT HO, KM, AP	Report of WS participants opinions about definition and perceptions
Panel LIDA	May 2016	AMT, KM, FS, Ap, VC	Report of participants

			opinion and ASIA first contacts
Analysis of data	Ongoing	ALL	Taxonomy
Ontology definition terms, properties and relationships	June	VC, FS	Ontology
Formal description SKOS	June	VC, FS	Website

Milestones

Literature review

Ana Pervan has completed a literature review about data curation on September 30th, 2015.

After going through 100 articles, two points are clear:

- Firstly, data curator is often confused for knowledge manager and in some cases with data librarian. This may be due to the very thin border between skills and roles these three types of information professionals have in practice. Since data curators don't only work in libraries, but also in research institutes, private cultural heritage foundations, government and NGO's, these thin lines become blurred in job advertisements.
- Secondly, the role of data curator according to the literature is flexible. It is evolving and shaping according to trends in information technology and user's needs. Therefore data curators are in these documents observed as information professionals with three main roles: supportive of research by providing data curation training to specific groups of users; as embedded in the research by following user's research plan; and as observers of the research because they are sometimes lacking specific domain based knowledge required to curate research data.

The literature review represents a bit of everything - curating data in academic and scientific libraries, research centers, in collaboration with archives, museums and galleries, and governmental institution. Presented 100 articles cover the topic of the role of data curator from the following aspects:

- Labour market – articles that examine data curation skills advertised in job posts
- Collaboration – roles data curators/knowledge managers have in (interdisciplinary) research

Bibliography is placed in an excel table and it is divided into 5 columns: resource, abstract, key words about the skills, roles and working environment of data curators, affiliation and notes.

You will notice that many key words are: digital repository, data preservation, training, curriculum and data curators. This is because majority of articles connect data curators with the creating and maintaining institutional repository, which many authors consider being an axel of scholarly communication. It is also because data curation goes hand in hand with data preservation skills and updating professional competences according to changes in information technology.

Furthermore, curriculum and data curation reflects on the academic LIS community and the aim to update the professional training and education according to needs of the labour market.

The Ana bibliography can be found here:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=10CdPKJoF74MXP8rnUP310ED2XBNIULdDw_2n1lrBQ4g

Job description

Phase one of the IFLA Data Curator research project consisted of a quantitative content analysis of job listings for data curators and related positions. The source data for this analysis were extracted from multiple sources, with a majority (more than 98%) scraped from the Code4Lib and IASSIST websites. The initial data set included 6051 job announcements. From there the database was winnowed to 441 data curator positions using both automated and hand coding, with 54% classified as composed of “primary” data curation responsibilities and 46% as “secondary”. This final database is preliminary in nature as it is likely to change as our research deepens.

Because of their source these results showed a selection bias towards positions located in the United States, though 34 countries in all were included in the database, and 12 countries were represented among the positions coded as data curators.

The second phase of the study provided an opportunity to gain insight into the practice of data curation and look at the roles and responsibilities from the perspective of information professionals working in the field. Interviews were a primary source of data and were supplemented by questionnaires and documentary evidence. Interviews followed a semi-structured protocol and focused on the participant's' job functions, work activities, distribution of responsibilities, and skills and competencies.

The report prepared by Krystyna is shared here:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=0BxYEZGxfpryTWG9SRG5RRTh3VUZxRGpEYjRsUWtubTVWOGIZ>

The table listing the job positions is shared here:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1OyEFVAjF-jh6nQp2GQ-Pg-QpSmfxa5XCgSsHA0OZCAg>

Ontology

Vittore Casarosa as a possible first step to arrive at an ontology for Data Curation, has prepared the term extraction from the corpus of 100 articles selected from Ana Pervan. A first match has been done between the automated extracted terms and job descriptions terms.

Vittore has shared the Excel table with the first list of terms with the Team here:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fGUDxx4NGu-qTiP8S0BdfHbmNj4nGzeEmRPb22k2xBo/edit?usp=sharing>

In order to try and extract "key concepts" from the 120 papers that had been put together by Ana, I have used a free tool called KD (Keyphrases Digger), developed at the University of Trento (<https://dh.fbk.eu/technologies/kd>). To see if there were differences (and there are,

but difficult to interpret) I ran the tool on three different corpora. One containing only the abstracts, one containing only the papers, and one containing both. I then tried to put the results together in "Summary Results".

The second list of terms is listed here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KKDZ8BAu9_88q_Ds1QFRLTtiovBPKRvjuMUnCHpKyOE/edit?usp=sharing

The translation in the main languages of the definitions should start soon.

Interviews and analysis of data are ongoing.

Final results are expected in October and Project final report in the end of the year.